

Pitch title: Dismantling the Fish-Oil Trap: SyMO3's Plant-Based Omega-3 Solution

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Spin-out name: SyMO3: Systems Engineering for Microalgae Omega-3s.

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Abstract:

Known as the "fish-oil trap," static supply essential of Omega-3 Poly-unsaturated Fatty Acids (PUFAs) from traditional wild fish sources combined with growing consumer demand has led to increasing volatility in fish oil prices. At SyMO3, we aim to dismantle this trap by delivering affordable, plant-based omega-3 oils sustainably sourced from microalgae. Our systems engineering approach combines precision fermentation with optimized cultivation systems to achieve efficient, renewable omega-3 production in a fully traceable manner. Our approach maximizes efficiency across every step of the production cycle, from strain selection to cultivation, harvesting, and extraction, enabling a consistent, high-quality product at scale. By shifting omega-3 production away from overfished marine sources, we offer a renewable solution that supports food, nutraceutical, and pharmaceutical sectors in their transition to sustainable, plant-based ingredients. Currently at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 4, SyMO3 is on track to reach TRL 7 by early 2026, marking our progression from pilot-scale validation toward a commercially viable solution. With targeted R&D and strategic partnerships, SyMO3 aims to become a leading source for sustainable omega-3s, addressing both market demand and ecological imperatives.

Keywords

Microalgae biotechnology, Precision fermentation, Sustainable Omega-3s.

Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

TRL 4 - technology validated in lab